

Appendix G: Sensitivity analysis results

Aspect evaluated	Scenario 1 (pre-2019 excluded)	Scenario 2 (moderate-to-high quality excluded)	Total impact	What remains the same (85–90 %)	What changes (10–15 %)
Classification of theories	< 5 % change	< 5 % change	< 5 %	PMT, TPB, GDT, SDT, PsyCap, BBT, AET, EI remain as predominant/emerging paradigms	Social Bond Theory and Psychological Contract Theory lose prominence
Key behavioral findings	15–20 % change	15–20 % change	15–20 %	Stress/fatigue, fear as a double-edged sword, emotion-focused vs. problem-focused coping	Psychological Ownership, Daily Emotional Fluctuations (ESM), Emotional Inoculation, Self-Control Trait
Recommended profiling dimensions	10 % change	10 % change	0,1	Personality (Big Five), Emotional Intelligence, Motivational, Coping Style, Healthcare Role/Context	Self-Control Capacity and Organizational Commitment/Contract Breach; Gender-tailored deterrence
Overall structural integrity	85–90 % intact	85–90 % intact	10–15 %	Main paradigms and profiling recommendations remain identical	Loss of specific contextual nuances (cultural collectivism, daily emotion tracking)
Number of remaining studies	76	76	—	—	—

Note: The excluded studies were: McCormac et al., (2018), Fagan (2017), D’Arcy et al., (2017), Anwar et al., (2016), Moody et al., (2018), Ifinedo (2017), Savoli et al., (2017), Boss et al., (2015), Burns et al., (2017), Posey et al., (2015), Blythe et al., (2018), Sher et al.,(2016), Menard et al., (2018), Kraushaar et al., (2025), Lahcen et al., (2020), and Lee et al., (2023). The synthesis was repeated manually with the remaining 76 studies using the same thematic approach.